

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW PROTOCOL

Review title: Graves' Orbitopathy following Alemtuzumab treatment for Multiple Sclerosis: a Systematic Review and Real-World Insights

Review objectives: The objective of this systematic review is to investigate the clinical and immunological features, management, and epidemiology of Graves' orbitopathy (GO) following alemtuzumab (ALEM) treatment in multiple sclerosis (MS) patients. Additional pharmacovigilance and institutional cases will be used to further synthesize real-world data.

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Searches: A systematic search according to the PRISMA guidelines will be performed in PubMed, Scopus, and Embase databases from inception, to identify studies that meet the inclusion criteria. No language restrictions will be applied.

Using MeSH, Emtree terms and text words, the following search string will be applied:

('alemtuzumab'/exp OR alemtuzumab) AND ('endocrine ophthalmopathy'/exp OR 'endocrine ophthalmopathy' OR 'ted' OR 'thyroid eye disease' OR 'graves orbitopathy' OR 'graves ophthalmopathy' OR 'orbitopathy')

Study design: This review will include published interventional studies, observational studies, case reports and series describing and detailing GO cases after treatment with ALEM for MS.

Inclusion criteria: (I) any type of study design; (II) patients diagnosed with MS; (III) patients previously treated with ALEM for MS; (IV) documented development of GO following ALEM treatment.

Exclusion criteria: (I) reports with no cases of GO after ALEM; (II) any detailed data on GO features; (III) GO diagnosed after ALEM treatment for other reasons than MS

Pharmacovigilance data from the FAERS database and institutional case series will also be analyzed separately.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Condition being studied

GO occurring after immune reconstitution therapy with ALEM.

Population

Patients with relapsing-remitting MS treated with ALEM who developed GO.

Intervention(s) or exposure(s)

ALEM treatment.

Comparator(s) or control(s)

Not applicable.

OUTCOMES TO BE ANALYSED

Main outcomes: Clinical characteristics of GO-f-ALEM including detailed severity and activity (CAS) scores, latency from ALEM to GO, TRAb levels, thyroid function, treatment approach to both thyroid dysfunction and GO

Measures of effect

Means and standard deviations (SDs) for continuous variables, frequencies and percentages for categorical variables.

Additional outcomes: GO-f-ALEM epidemiology (comparing literature data vs pharmacovigilance database on eye disorders reported for ALEM vs institutional case series data), risk factors

Measures of effect

Means and standard deviations (SDs) for continuous variables, frequencies and percentages for categorical variables.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS**Study Selection**

Three reviewers will independently screen records by titles and abstracts. Full-text will be reviewed to confirm eligibility. Disagreements will be solved by discussion. Further, references of the selected studies will be screened to identify additional relevant papers for the review.

Data Extraction

The following data will be extracted:

- Study characteristics: year, country, type of publication.
- Patient demographics: age, gender, ethnicity.
- Generic risk factors: smoking status and family history of autoimmune or thyroid diseases
- Drug-Related Factors: dose of Alemtuzumab, latency period between drug administration and the onset of thyroid dysfunction and/or GO
- Thyroid dysfunction characteristics (type of thyroid dysfunction observed, presence of goitre).

- Thyroid Function and Autoantibodies (fluctuations in thyroid function, fluctuating TRAb and peak TRAb levels, data on anti-thyroglobulin antibodies (AbTg) and anti-thyroid peroxidase antibodies (AbTPO) levels)
- Treatment of Thyroid dysfunction (medical treatment, radioactive iodine, thyroidectomy).
- GO characteristics (detailed and cumulative CAS score, proptosis, diplopia, visual field, ocular muscle involvement, and CT scan findings)
- GO Treatment Modalities (use of lubricants, selenium, oral and i.v. steroids, immunomodulatory drugs, monoclonal antibodies, need for ophthalmic surgery).

RISK OF BIAS (QUALITY) ASSESSMENT

The risk of bias in included studies will be assessed with dedicated tools.

For observational studies, the risk of bias will be evaluated using the Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies of Interventions (ROBINS-I) tool by Cochrane. Studies will be classified as having a low risk, moderate risk, high risk, or critical risk of bias.

For randomized controlled trials (RCTs), the risk of bias will be assessed using the second version of the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool for randomized trials (RoB 2) by Cochrane. Studies will be classified as having a low risk of bias, some concerns, or a high risk of bias.

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

The systematic review will be conducted in accordance with the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions. Means and standard deviations (SDs) will be calculated for continuous variables. For categorical variables, frequencies and percentages will be reported. All analyses will be performed using R software (version 4.4.2)

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members

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